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Exploitation of the surface chemistry of $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{CoO}_{3-\delta}$ thin-film solid-oxide electrodes for the improvement of solid/gas interfaces

Ozden Celikbilek (1), Andrea Cavallaro (1), Gwilherme Kerherve (1), Ainara Aguadero (1), John A. Kilner (1,2), Stephen J. Skinner (1)

(1) Department of Materials, Imperial College London

Prince Consort Road, SW7 2BP London/United Kingdom

(2) International Institute for Carbon-Neutral Energy Research (I2CNER), Kyushu University, 744 Motoooka, Nishi-ku, 819-0395 Fukuoka/Japan

Contact authors: www.EFCF.com/ContactRequest

Abstract

Advances in materials design in solid-state energy devices have opened up unprecedented opportunities for development in recent years. This work focuses on understanding, controlling and optimising the mechanism of oxygen reduction reactions (ORR) in complex transition metal oxides, in particular $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{CoO}_{3-\delta}$ (LSC) thin films grown at different substrate temperatures by Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD). We investigated the surface to bulk elemental distribution of the films with low-energy ion scattering spectroscopy and aimed to correlate it with the electrochemical activity and stability of the films.[1] Although the initial ORR activity of the film grown at high substrate temperature was better than the one grown at low substrate temperature, interestingly, it showed 2-times higher degradation rate in the long-term electrochemical tests. The better stability of the film grown at low substrate temperature is attributed to the segregation of Sr into protruding particles. In this way, Co content reached stoichiometry in the remaining surface. This study emphasizes the influence of processing temperature and post thermal treatments on the electrochemical activity and stability of the PLD films.

- [1] Celikbilek, O., Cavallaro, A., Kerherve, G., Fearn, S., Chaix-Pluchery, O., Aguadero, A., Kilner, J. A., Skinner, S. J. 2020, "Surface Restructuring of Thin-Film Electrodes Based on Thermal History and Its Significance for the Catalytic Activity and Stability at the Gas/Solid and Solid/Solid Interfaces," ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces, 12, pp. 34388–34401.

1. Introduction

Thin-film deposition techniques, such as pulsed laser deposition (PLD), grabbed significant attention over the last decade thanks to the easy tunability of conductivity and ion exchange/diffusion kinetics. The substrate choice, substrate temperature and background gas pressure during deposition become decisive on the microstructure, crystallinity and the stress/strain in a film. However, high-temperature operational requirements of ceramic solid oxide cells (SOC) may also affect the points mentioned above and thus be taken into consideration.

The (LaSr)CoO_{3-δ} based thin films were extensively studied in the literature as model electrodes due to their high electrochemical activity for oxygen reduction reactions (ORR). Few reports studied La_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}CoO_{3-δ} (LSC64) composition on single crystal (100)-oriented yttria-stabilised zirconia (YSZ) substrates with varying substrate temperatures and pressures during PLD deposition.[2-6] From these reports, a similar trend in terms of film crystallinity and microstructure can be deduced. In particular, a study by Cai *et al.* compared the ORR activity and the stability of LSC64 films deposited by the PLD at 450 and 650 °C substrate temperatures.[5] Both films exhibited oriented columnar microstructures on the single-crystal YSZ support. The authors showed that the film deposited at 450 °C were catalytically more active and stable than the one deposited at 650 °C. The enhancement with low temperature deposition was attributed to several combined effects; nano-porosity originating likely due to partly crystalline nature of the films, more uniform and nearly stoichiometric cations in the as-prepared states, less Sr segregation and phase separation upon annealing. Few others reported much higher performance LSC electrodes by post-annealing the films deposited at low temperatures (< 100 °C) and high oxygen pressures (> 0.1 mbar).[7-8] These films typically had large porous channels separating highly disordered nano-scale grain clusters.

All these previous reports indicate the importance of thermal history and processing of the SOC electrode films on the catalytic activity and stability. However, these studies lack a systematic and comparative analysis of the surface chemistry at the nanometer scale and below. Here, we studied two LSC64 films by PLD with different processing temperatures and thermal history. Detailed information can be found in reference [1]. Electrochemical activity and long-term stability were monitored by impedance spectroscopy and the surface elemental distributions by low-energy ion scattering spectroscopy. A correlation between thermal history, catalytic activity/stability and cationic distribution was evidenced.

2. Experiments

For thin film deposition, PLD targets were prepared from a commercial La_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}CoO_{3-δ} (LSC64) powder supplied by Praxair (99.9% purity). The films were deposited using a Neocera pulsed laser deposition system (COMPex 205 F, Coherent) with a 248 nm KrF excimer laser with 25 ns pulse duration. The laser repetition rate was 10 Hz and the target to substrate distance was set to 5 cm. The partial pressure of oxygen gas was 0.043 mbar. The substrate temperature was set as 100 °C and 750 °C. After the deposition, the oxygen partial pressure in the chamber was increased to 800 mbar to oxidize the films *in situ*. Consequently, the temperature was reduced at a 20 °C min⁻¹ rate to room temperature before removal of the substrate. Single-side polished Si (001) substrates were used for structural and microstructural characterizations. For electrochemical characterization, polycrystalline pellets of 10% Gd doped ceria (GDC) (Praxair, 99.9%) were used as substrates. The film thicknesses were around 200 nm. The films deposited at 750 °C are referred to as high-temperature-grown, or simply as HT-grown, and those deposited at 100

°C followed by annealing at 600 °C for 4 h in ambient air post-deposition as post-annealed low-temperature-grown or simply as post-annealed LT-grown films.

The microstructure of the films was studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using a Zeiss Auriga Cross microscope operating at an accelerating voltage of 5 kV and ~7 mm working distance. The surface morphology of the films was examined using an Asylum MFP-3D atomic force microscopy (AFM) instrument. AFM data were analyzed using the open-source software Gwyddion 2.53. The micrographs were taken on 1.0 x 1.0 μm^2 scan area using 512 x 512 px.

The electrochemical characterization of the films was performed using a Solartron 1260 frequency response analyzer, and in the frequency range of 13 MHz - 0.1 Hz at an amplitude of 20 mV. The samples were measured at the open-circuit potential. The samples were contacted with Pt grids (Goodfellow, 1500 wire/inches) and then sandwiched between Al_2O_3 blocks with gas channels, which were pressed to ensure maximum contact points. The impedance diagrams were fitted with electrical equivalent circuits using the ZView 2 software.

The outermost atomic surface and sub-surface chemical compositions were measured with a Qtac100 low-energy ion scattering spectroscopy (LEIS) instrument (ION-TOF GmbH, Münster, Germany) operated with normal incidence Ne^+ (5 keV) as primary beam sources coupled with a secondary ion beam sputtering source of 1 keV Ar^+ incident at 45° to normal. The primary beam scanning area was set as 1000 x 1000 μm^2 and the rastered area with the secondary ion beam was 1500 x 1500 μm^2 .

3. Results

The surface topography of the LSC64 films was investigated by SEM and AFM. Figure 1a and b show the SEM top-views of the post-annealed LT-grown and HT-grown films deposited on oriented Si (001) substrates by PLD. The post-annealed film appeared to have homogeneously distributed protruding particles over the entire surface, whereas the HT-grown film was flat and smooth. Cracking can be observed in the HT-grown film, which is a result of differences in thermal expansion coefficients (TEC) between the films and the substrates. The cracking in the LT-grown film was avoided during deposition by setting slow heating and cooling rates (2 and 3 °C min^{-1}) during post-annealing.

Figure 1c and d show the surface topography of the films analyzed by AFM. The grain sizes were estimated to be $\sim 30 \pm 10$ nm for the post-annealed LT-grown, whereas those of the HT-grown film showed $\sim 60 \pm 10$ nm. The root mean square (rms) roughness of the films was calculated to be 3.24 ± 0.1 nm for the post-annealed film and 2.09 ± 0.1 nm for the HT-grown film. A horizontal line was drawn both in Figure 1c and d to measure the height of the protruding particles. Particularly, many particles reaching up to ~ 30 nm from the surface was observed for the post-annealed film (Figure 1c). Although the HT-grown film had a lower roughness compared to the post-annealed LT-grown film, the light-coloured particle under the horizontal line in Figure 1d was found to be ~ 20 nm high from the rest of the surface.

Figure 1 Top-view SEM micrographs (a, b) and AFM images (c, d) of LSC64 films deposited by the PLD on Si substrates: a) and c) showing post-annealed LT-grown film, b) and d) showing HT-grown film.[1] (<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsami.0c08308>) Reprinted with the permission of the American Chemical Society. Further permissions related to the material excerpted should be directed to the ACS.

The ORR activity and the stability of the films were assessed by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy on symmetrical cells using GDC electrolytes. Figure 2 shows the Nyquist plots of LT-grown and HT-grown films measured at 500 °C, showing the 1st stable impedance plots (Figure 2a and c) and the 100th (Figure 2b and d). The LT-grown film post-annealed in situ. It took a few hours to get a stable Nyquist plot for the LT-grown film, since crystallization took place during the measurements. At least two resistive contributions are visible in the impedance plots. The corresponding equivalent circuit diagram is shown in Figure 2e. The resistance at the high-frequency arc (10^4 - 10^1 Hz) was attributed to the interfacial charge transfer resistance (denoted as R_i) and the low-frequency arc (10^1 - 10^{-1} Hz) to the surface resistance of the electrodes (denoted as R_s). L represents the inductance of the wires, R_{series} is the series resistance of the electrolyte, and both R_i and R_s are connected in parallel to a constant phase element (CPE). It can be observed that the post-annealed LT-grown film showed higher R_i values compared with the HT-grown one (Figure 2a and b). Although the R_s value of the HT-grown film was smaller than the LT-grown film in the initial measurement, it degraded faster. Figure 2f demonstrates the degradation rate between the 1st and 100th measurement at a constant temperature of 500 °C. It can be seen that the R_s value of the HT-grown film degraded ~ 2 times faster than the LT-grown film ($\sim 2.40\%/h$ vs $1.12\%/h$).

Figure 2. Nyquist plots of the 1st and the 100th measurements of (a,b) post-annealed LT-grown and (c,d) HT-grown films measured at 500 °C in OCV in ambient air. A dwell time of 1 h was set between the measurements. Equivalent circuit element is shown in e). The evolution of R_s as a function of time at a stable 500 °C is shown in f). [1] (<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsami.0c08308>) Reprinted with the permission of the American Chemical Society. Further permissions related to the material excerpted should be directed to the ACS.

Next, LEIS analysis was used to survey the distribution of cation composition from the outermost surface layer to a few tens of nanometers below the surface. Figure 3 shows the LEIS depth profiling of the films. The data provide qualitative information and compare the cationic compositional evolution between the two films. The x-scale in the depth profiles refers to sputtering Ar^+ ion dose, in which, the small values indicate outermost to sub-surface composition, whereas, increased values refer to the sub-surface to bulk composition. The analysis depth at Ar^+ ion sputter density of 85×10^{15} atoms/ cm^2 corresponds to approximately 18 nm depth. Horizontal lines with the same colour of each element were added as a guide to the eye, and they indicate the approximate bulk composition, deduced from the steady data points at high Ar^+ ion dose.

Figure 3 LEIS depth profiling of as-obtained films of a) post-annealed LT-grown, and b) HT-grown films; after long term stability tests at 500 °C for 100 h of c) post-annealed LT-grown and d) HT-grown films.[1] (<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsami.0c08308>) Reprinted with the permission of the American Chemical Society. Further permissions related to the material excerpted should be directed to the ACS.

The enrichment of Sr in the outermost surface layer in the as-obtained films has been proven for both films in this study (Figure 3a and b), as has been previously observed with other Sr-containing perovskites.[9-11] At the same depth, La and Co were depleted at the surface and a few atomic layers below. A marked difference between the films was observed in the sub-surface, approximately between 1 nm and 10 nm below the surface. Notably, a region with highly depleted Sr and increased La concentration appeared in the post-annealed LT-grown film, whereas an enriched Sr layer was observed for the HT-grown film which continued up to ~ 6 nm below the surface.

Figure 3c and d investigate the chemical distribution of the same films after long-term annealing at 500 °C in ambient air for 100 h. It can be observed that the outermost surface layer of the post-annealed LT-grown film entirely consisted of Sr-based species (Figure 3c). However, Co concentration substantially increased immediately below this layer and reached its bulk stoichiometry. The HT-grown film showed a mixed La- and Sr-based termination (Figure 3d). Below the outermost surface layer, Sr remained in excess for a few nanometers, while Co remained deficient.

4. Conclusions

This study focuses on the influence of thermal history on the catalytic activity and stability of $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{CoO}_{3-\delta}$ (LSC64) thin films. The films were grown by Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) at different substrate temperatures. The microstructure, surface topography and elemental distribution of the films were investigated and compared with the electrochemical response. In terms of ORR activity, the initial response was in favour of HT-grown film. However, long-term tests appeared to influence the catalytical stability significantly. The post-annealed LT-grown film showed two-times smaller grain size than the HT-grown film, with a rough surface comprising ~ 30 nm thick protruding particles. LEIS analysis indicated that Sr segregation enhanced near the surface, leaving a deficient Sr layer at the subsurface. Sr segregation is believed to proceed through clustering into the protruding particles as observed in SEM and AFM. Therefore, this type of segregation enabled the remaining surface to reveal catalytically important Co cations. On the other hand, the flat and smooth surface of the HT-grown film led to a more homogeneously distributed and thicker Sr-rich surface region near the surface compared with the post-annealed LT-grown film. Thus, thermally induced surface restructuring is believed to be the reason for the differences in the catalytic activity and long-term stability of the films.

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